

PERFORMER OF THE SONG IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSIC WORLDWIDE IMPORTANCE.

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Annotation. Information about the introduction of the article into the life of the present society in the development of the art of Henry the Song of Folic we have a human life rolled in its expression, we have not folk custom, traditions, rituals, holidays.

Keywords. Mixed personal, thinking, synthetic, primitive, the ancient faith, mythological, miraculous, imagination, rites, ritual.

The song of the genre in the development of music worldwide performer - the nation with the formation of human speech type and the genre of artistic creativity without oral qorishiq also begun to arise outdated. Various forms of artistic creation in samples that contain a synthetic primitive people thought the number maishat all aspects of the business and is tightly bound with ancient mythology and religious people e'tiqodiy vision, primary research, that is, empirical knowledge about nature and society reflection of the imagination. However, the ancient arrived folkloric such samples are incomplete, but some parts of the tracks and their lives and the lifestyle of the people associated with a variety of regional and look at the picture, people, traditions, rituals and holidays in the structure, some written sources in folklore saved without the balance in the

next period recorded in the works, he said.

The song is the translator of the human spirit. Beshik up from the grave it is to listen to the song. Agree with hearts will describe the song. Also, the sad days, the song is also quvonchlidamlarida hamnafas, this is anticipation of the song, the song creates. As reported, is to say that allah bring the spirit into the human body through song. So, I find their lifestyle and in the song of in'ikosini his whole life. In the song, the life of the people, the national customs, values and traditions with all facets of charm and has its own characteristics. The mindset of the people in the song, outlook, and the specific nature is manifested.

Genre analysis of uzbekistan also the song at the musician, his artistic incredibly jilvakorlikka wealth-yu, insightful research by scientists was that many researchers ifodaviy line. Record is very much a part of them, and has become our spiritual heritage-was raised. Especially in this field, national qo'shiqshunoslar Muzayyaia Alaviya, doctor of philological sciences, professor t. Mirzaev, M. Djurayev, doctor of philological sciences A. D. O'rayeva Musoqulov, r. nosirov scientists, researchers and other songs of the lyrics of the genre of melodic n. ortiqmatov colorful, poetik was a comprehensive analysis of features. More well-known scientists Follow pensions "of the bunch-the pearl of the bunch called" song is one of the remarkable achievements of Uzbek people gathered to be published too. Also, our musician was to learn that at the heart of the people's artist of uzbekistan, great importance is given to research it. In particular, professor o. Safarovning, "blessed Tuychi, sweetheart-sweetheart" associated with marriage ceremony ceremony songs are included in the game, "buxor far" and "Mavrigi" force works significant contribution. Only the specific content in the book category of the category of the historical poetik ge would bukhara found on the net, based on the composition and properties of the execution of the method was interpreted with the skill. Also tash-old y. rajabiy published on the academic side "of Uzbek folk music" songs and has gathered of

the people in the book of the sample. The successful side of the book the people of uzbekistan, which is rich in terms of content and genre of the song recorded songs in the genre zkanligi recognized the same theme and your team are allocated to specific groups. The labor of the people song lyrics, wedding besides, satirik and yumoristik songs, mourning songs, seasonal songs, and modern moral songs, children's folklore in munojot, counsel see also new songs in the genre of the song is a wholesale example.

The wealth and the means of the artistic content of the song finally at the level of the fine to specific wealth. The verses in them meaningful phrases, with the wealth and artistic pieces to the means, remain engraved in the heart of man is different from that with other genres. Xalqona spirit, and the particular xalqona teranlik creativity is reflected. In the song the cloth, wipes, rings, spikes, snake, flower, nightingales, apples, lola. river horse, that there are tools such as fine art, each one of them acquires a symbolic meaning. Thus, it wipes everything, ishq-the symbol of love. Ma'shukaning give the cloth to fall in love with life and along with it, it was rizolik is to be together. However, the most high, to fall in love with dream. Life - mamot is listed as the winner in the fight. The image wipes in the literature of the image is written symbol means. G'azal the outbreak of alisher navoi in the sorrow of love in the form of wipes, every qatida much in the threads of love and devotion during the nine monthsjassam is expressed in an artistic way, that is:

Yog'lig'in, I tikarsen eyk, needle mujgon my cellar

The pattern I make in the life of tori oni is his bond.

The people of uzbekistan in the tools stand out with colorful song lyrics fine art. In him, every expression is similar to, once again, the rhythm, to revive the person and environment to a variety of sifatlash as a symbol of the spiritual, thus performs the function in the expression of a certain piece of the image. Thus, the famous "Sunbula" has been engraved in the minds of each child to

remain on the song like a lifetime. O'x this will be mostly focused on portrait painting shatish firoq love to kungli any burning ointment:

In this world there is

Heart-whole-heart.

The oven is made from paper,

The flowers are made from wood.

Step bchilsin your flowers!

The same thing logically, this is living in the human realm, unless of course he won something, one thing will yuqolib. How qatida happiness unhappiness is the feeling of unfathomable power spent, grief, anxiety, bitterness, and longing like o'kinch will also be hidden. Issued in exchange for the losses to human happiness. This is the condition of life. The paper is made as of the oven, never, never fulfill the function of the wood, the flowers full, without loss of happiness to be achieved not through the truth of life similar to this bright outlined. A lot of imagination occurs in the song apples, apple also oshiqqlar ishq between folklore-the symbol of love. It is more accurate expression family, children of the dream, see the image:

The elegance of apple from

Looks of the pieces.

Shabnam leaves fell to

His devona of

Love the elegance of apple to keep it very difficult to reach him, to find himself a companion worthy of the most vital problem is that if the pieces of his children as to achieve the glorious blessings even greater happiness. Shabnam-the same road, to put part of the steps towards happiness, is blameless. Devona is the owner of z if it is not the actions of these efforts.

The art of repetition in the song occupies a special place, This takrorlar words in undov in verse and performs certain tasks and each one is used a lot in

naqarot poetik:

Oh, ukajonim-yey,
 Quralay my eye-yey.
 Yellow have rangin
 Shul brow pencil-arc

Like the work in the quote, that ukajon - very close to the quralay - lots of the children as the eyes beautiful eyes, yellow color - hajr, suffering from the world of firoq tashkari “yey” undov come to be served more kuchaytyrib passions to describe emotions.

In the song sweetheart-sweetheart occurs in many takrori. This fact moxiyati sweetheart sweetheart- is the expression of the wedding ceremony. It is one of the traditional types of the phrase associated with this ceremony, the song in rhythm to the music it performs important functions in creating:

Tile qoshing say
 Black eye my brother, sweetheart-sweetheart.
 My brother sweet words, sweetheart-sweetheart,
 Let's see a show qoshing,
 My soul my brother-yey.sweetheart-sweetheart.

There is increasing interest more people in our time to the playback of the song. The people they sing a variety of tunes in the genre in the way it is progressing, and national. Especially, people's artist of uzbekistan of Farrux Zokirov, Star Tbsp, Ozodbek Nazarbekov. Gulsanam Mamazoitova, the elegance of the honored artist of the republicRaximova la, Xurshid Rasulov, like the song of our people in the repertoire of artists of uzbekistan national to enjoy.

Song – in the broad sense of poetic-musical genre, vocal music, most popular, based on the type of the shape more busy, as well as the works of other poems to sing is an expression of the total. People related to creativity, composer, and composers have created, the direction of popular music-songs is

the difference. Origin, genre, and content depending on ceremony songs, song, mass, city, peasants, children, household, military, lyrics, songs, and other cancers is separated. The song lower diapa-zo of the compact, or the development of the music busy busy-naqarot influences on the form-gan, the sounds in words and tunes up system intonatsiya the community, the ministry of poems in the text, committed to the development of emotional content expressed as the results are characterized by a general artistic way. The more specific side of the song — text poems and songs of the form of the mutual ratio structures of the same size in the poem-busy tone-on period is. The text of the song of the poem is clear, composites-expressed in certain opinion of each handle with competence siya tugal stand out. If you have specific national characteristics of the people in the song of the east in central asia ir (jir), national o'lan my lap, with a name like yalla is referred. Creativity on the basis of these composers in the twentieth century, the development of the modern form of the song I can find. European professional in the art of music in the middle ages, the poet - singer truver trubadurlar in france and in germany minnezingerlarning works of art meysterzingerlar samples, created during the renaissance period, many Italian canzonetta for voice, nemischa Lied, chanson franiuzcha the centuries – songs from the tuc in the style of ac mass gomofoniya taking the eighteenth, in the period of composites romantizm-torlar in the song of creation, the development of mass of the twentieth wide adoption composed songs, pop songs and music of the development of other professional stage. From the poet P..Beranje, R. Byorns also r.zatov, V. Visotskiy and others in uzbekistan Hamza, Khabibiy, Sobir Abdulla, Mirtemir, Chustiy, Complete T. P. Meek, by n. narzullaev, Muhammad, Joseph, after academician e. Jabborov J., and others-the song of poetry in the development of great services.

The song in the narrow sense – the people of uzbekistanthe genre ko'shib boshlanuvchi rhyme with dida, basically, 7-8 xij fingers to'rtlik tunes in weight

term-shaped handle aytim type. The first poem to'rtlik kofi city-in the world of aaa. aava, or aavs can be in the ratio of aavv. The song of uzbekistan-four poems in the world are usually the first paragraph quote, and to sing them, which is the basis was formed from the combination of structures relative tugal tone. 2-4 sing is the number of structures, their mutual ratios while the key phrase repeat, to a certain extent developed as a means to change or end with a new sentence consists. The songs of uzbekistan, singing, as opposed to the small voice within basically, kvinta - seks is in the range, sometimes within the accompaniment is executed. Tone tone is the measure of a song, the lyrics are basically in the topic occurs in the sample. Kuychanlik cho'zimli tone has features in other songs in the world are they more on the eve of the completion of the song appears. They contain almost certain special parts of the manual naqarot in the song, sometimes repeated the words coming naqarot small professional executive function, as well as "soul", "sweetheart", "dod-o" like undov-undalma phrases will be used in tracking. Uzbek composer of the twentieth century, and especially, belonging to the genre of the song is most creative at from the perspective of other genres, including lap, yalla, singing, dial the feature includes, have undergone certain changes. In particular, in them busy-naqarot structures, jo'rnavoz musical and dance forms can also be seen. From the composer of uzbekistan Y. Rajabiy, K. Jabborov, Faxriddin Sodiqov, T. Jalilov, G'.Toshmatov, N. Khasanov, M. Mirzaev, b. aliyev, R. Tursunov and others, the most T. Sodiqov, by m. burkhanov, M. Leviyev, S. Yudakov, A. Otajonov, F. Nazarov, A. Nazarov, F. Alimov, K. Kamilov, A. Muxamedov for children, it doubles.Tears At Shva, Il.Akbarov N. norxo'jaev by Anvar Ergashev, A. Mansurov, direction variety Sh.Ramazonov, Ik.Akbarov, E. Solixov, D. Omonullayeva, A. Rasulov and creativity in the genre of the songs have a significant other.

The study of folk song of uzbekistan national madaniyatimizga the unlimited mercy of love and respect our sample. The creativity of our people, the

count of each song, and added high moral ummoni an invaluable treasure.

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